

Analysis of Large-Scale Thermal Dynamics

Elena Vasquez, Liam O'Connor

University of Cambridge, UK, Cambridge Institute of Energy Research

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to develop a meso-scale annular type combustor that uses two types of coaxial cylindrical flames, rich premixed flame and diffusion flame. The combustor consists of inner and outer porous tubes, and rich C_3H_8 -air mixture and air issued, respectively, through the inner tube outwardly and through the outer tube inwardly, forms a cylindrical stagnation plane sandwiched by the inner rich premixed flame and the outer diffusion flame. A petal type flame was also observed in the downstream of the cylindrical flames. Maintaining a constant equivalence ratio ϕ_i and flow rate q_i of the rich mixture, the overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} is controlled by varying the air flow rate q_o of the outer tube. In order to investigate the combustion performance, the temperature was measured inside and at the outlet of the combustion chamber. The heat loss rate and exergy loss rate were evaluated from the obtained temperature data. The minimum values of the heat loss rate and exergy loss rate were 0.30 and 0.57, respectively. These loss rates were compared with the performance of other meso-scale combustors.

Article Info: Received: 29 November 2022 | Accepted: 13 January 2023 | Published online: 01 February 2023

Keywords: Functional Materials, Advanced Physics, Materials Science, Open Access

Key words : Combustion, Meso-scale combustor, Annular combustor, Heat loss rate, Exergy loss rate

1. Introduction

For very small power-supply systems and very small propulsion systems, the ultra-micro gas turbine and the micro rotary engine have been developed (Ju et al., 2015). Downsizing of combustors has many problems such as the increase in heat loss rate. Downsizing of combustors and quenching distance are closely connected to each other. As the quenching distance of hydrogen is smaller than that of hydrocarbon fuel, hydrogen has an advantage in downsizing of the combustor. However, considering the handling ability of both the combustor and a fuel bottle, use of a hydrocarbon fuel is considered suitable. Accordingly, many researchers have developed meso-scale combustors using hydrocarbon fuels.

There are several different types of meso-scale combustors: (1) the premixed flat flame type formed on a porous plate (Marbach et al., 2007), (2) the flat flame type formed in stagnation flow (Sakurai et al., 2013), (3) the flame type stabilized by the cavity (Fan et al., 2009; Wan et al., 2015), (4) the flame type formed in the vortex flow (Li et al., 2009; Shimokuri et al., 2015) and so forth. Sakurai et al. (2013) have developed a combustor that can be applied to the ultra-micro gas turbine. Shimokuri et al. (2015) have developed a thermoelectric power generation system with a meso-scale vortex combustor. Fan et al. (2009) and Li et al. (2009) have developed combustors for a thermophotovoltaic (TPV) power generation system. There are many combustor types and utilization purposes.

We investigated the extinction characteristics of a stretched cylindrical diffusion flame, and found that the flame strengthened with a decrease in the flame diameter (Suenaga et al., 2010a, 2011a). Application of this flame strengthening effect to the combustion in a very small domain is effective in downsizing the combustors. Therefore, we developed an annular type combustor that can form the cylindrical flame, and conducted research experiments (Suenaga et al., 2010b, 2011b). Our combustor consists of inner and outer porous tubes. A fuel-rich mixture is supplied

radially outwardly from the inner tube, and then the air is supplied radially inwardly from the outer tube. Since this combustor has a structure covering the combustion chamber with combustion air, the influence of the ambient air on heat loss of the combustor is considered to be small. In the present study, we reveal the flame structure by measuring

temperature distribution in the combustor, and then evaluate the heat loss rate of the combustor. Generally, thermal efficiency is used to evaluate the combustor performance. However, the setting equivalence ratio of the combustor is different in each of the previous researches. The difference in the equivalence ratio changes the generation rate of the entropy, meaning that an unavailable energy varies depending on the generation rate of entropy (Takagi et al., 2006). Since the increase in entropy means an increase in unavailable energy, it should also be considered unavailable energy in order to evaluate the performance of the combustor. Therefore, the combustor performance is evaluated using the exergy loss rate obtained by considering the heat loss rate and entropy generation rate, and compared with the performance of other micro-combustors.

2. Experimental setup and procedure

2.1 Combustor

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the annular type meso-scale combustor. The combustor's outer tube is made of brass, and has an outer diameter of 20 mm, length of 45 mm, inner diameter of 9 mm, and a depth of 39 mm. A stainless inner tube 1.2 mm in diameter is installed along the same axis as the outer tube. On the inner side of the outer

Figure 1. Schematic of the annular type micro-combustor Figure 2. Measurement points of the temperature tube, twelve 0.6-mm openings were made circumferentially along one line; 11 such lines with openings were aligned at 2-mm intervals in the axial direction. On the inner tube side, eight 0.3-mm openings were made circumferentially on one line; 21 such lines with openings were aligned at 1-mm intervals in the axial direction. The combustion chamber capacity is 2.44 cm³. The fuel used is propane (C₃H₈), and the oxidizer is air. By supplying air from the outer tube and a fuel-rich mixture from the inner tube, a double flame is formed: a cylindrical fuel-rich premixed flame inside and cylindrical diffusion flame outside. A cooling system was installed to maintain constant boundary conditions of the combustor's

external side. In this experiment, the equivalence ratio of the mixture supplied from the inner tube ϕ_i and the mixture flow rate q_i were maintained constant ($q_i=18.9 \text{ cm}^3/\text{s}$), and the overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} is calculated by the total flow rates of fuel and air supplied to the combustor and is controlled by changing the flow rate of air q_o supplied from the outer tube. Here, the mixture flow velocity, which is defined as the supplied mixture flow rate q_i divided by the surface area of the 20-mm-long mixture tube including the mixture supply openings, is set to 25 cm/s.

2.2 Method of measuring temperature

A thermocouple of Pt-Rh40%/Pt-Rh20%, 50 μm in wire diameter was used for the temperature measurement. The wires were coated in silica to prevent catalytic reaction on the surface. Radiative heat loss of the thermocouple was corrected by Kaskan's method (Kaskan, 1957). Conduction heat loss was not corrected. Temperature measurements were performed for the mixture equivalence ratio ϕ_i ranging from 1.5 to 4.0 and for the overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} ranging from 0.6 to 1.0. The measuring points of the temperature are shown in Fig. 2. When the center of the combustor outlet was set to the origin in the cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z), the temperature was measured in the r -direction $r = 1.5 \text{ mm}$ to 3.5 mm at 0.5 mm intervals, in the z -direction $z = 0 \text{ mm}$ to 37 mm at 1.0 mm intervals, and in the θ -direction $\theta = 0^\circ$ to 360° at 11.25° intervals. The standard deviation of the temperature data was large when the local extinction occurred, and the maximum value of standard deviation in each measurement point was 23.3 K.

2.3 Definitions of heat loss rate and exergy loss rate

In a preliminary experiment of burnt gas compositions by using a portable gas analyzer (testo-330), carbon monoxide CO concentrations in the dry burnt gas were less than 1 vol%. CO concentrations further reduce in the wet-burnt gas. In this study, therefore, we consider the situation in which the burnt gas consists of CO_2 , H_2O , O_2 , and N_2 , assuming that the fuel is completely burned. Heat loss rate η_{hl} is defined by the following formula (1).

$$\eta_{hl} = \frac{Q_{loss}}{H_f} = 1 - G_b c_{p,m} H_f (T_b - T_0) \quad (1)$$

Here, Q_{loss} is the amount of heat loss, H_f is the low calorific value, G_b is the burnt gas flow rate per unit fuel flow rate, $c_{p,m}$ is the constant pressure specific heat of burnt gas, T_b is the averaged burnt gas temperature at the burner exit and T_0 is the temperature of the combustor inlet. T_0 was set to 298.15 K.

In the open system such as this combustor, when momentum energy and potential energy are ignored, an exergy E is defined by the following formula (2) (Mizutani, 1989).

$$E = H - T_0 S = - \phi - \phi_0 \quad (2)$$

Here, H is enthalpy, T is temperature, and S is entropy. Signs without a subscript mean a condition before reaching the equilibrium value, and signs with subscript " ϕ " mean that the condition reaches the equilibrium value of $T_0 = 298.15 \text{ K}$. Exergy of burnt gas E_b is determined as the following formula.

$$E_b = (H_b - H_0) - T_0 S_b \quad (3)$$

$(H_b - H_0)$, S_b , S_0 of each component in the burnt gas were obtained from NIST-JANAF Thermochemical Tables (accessed on 30 June, 2015). Exergy loss rate $\eta_{ex,loss}$ is defined as follows.

$$\eta_{ex,loss} = 1 - \frac{E_b}{E_f} \quad (4)$$

Here, E_b and E_f are exergies of burnt gas and fuel, respectively.

We consider the relationship between $\eta_{ex,loss}$ and η_{hl} . Since it is commonly known as the relation $H_l \doteq E_f$, the formula (1) can be rewritten as formula (5).

$$\left(\underline{H} \quad H \right)$$

f

The second term of the right hand side is the loss due to the entropy generation. The exergy loss rate obtained in this study is expressed as the sum of the heat loss rate and generation rate of entropy.

3. Experimental results and discussion

3.1 Flame behaviors and temperature contours

Figure 3 shows the flame photographs and the temperature contours on the $r-\theta$ planes. Experimental conditions of Figs. 3 (a) and 3 (b) are $\varphi_i = 1.5$ and $\varphi_i = 3.0$ respectively, and φ_{all} is 0.7 constant in both figures. Here, φ_i is the equivalence ratio of the rich mixture supplied from the inner tube, and φ_{all} is the overall equivalence ratio calculated from the total flow rates of fuel and air supplied to the combustor. As shown in Fig. 2, when the center of the combustor outlet is set to the origin in the cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) , these temperature contours were obtained at $z = 20$ mm and $z = 0$ mm. $z = 20$ mm is near the downstream edge of the supply-openings of the inner and outer tubes, and $z = 0$ mm is the chamber outlet. In the photograph of Fig. 3 (a), the cylindrical flame is formed in the central region of the chamber and a petal-type flame is formed in the downstream side of the cylindrical flame. Here, the rich premixed flame and the diffusion flame are not observed individually. It is considered that these two flames are united. The petal-type flame can also be observed from the temperature contour measured at $z = 20$ mm.

According to the photograph in Fig. 3 (b), local extinctions of the petal-type flame and the cylindrical flame are observed. These local extinctions can also be observed from the temperature contour at $z = 20$ mm. We consider the reason why the cylindrical flame and petal-type flame observed in Fig. 3 (b) are extinguished locally. φ_{all} is controlled by air flow rate q_o supplied from the outer tube because equivalence ratio φ_i and flow rate q_i of the mixture supplied from the inner tube are fixed. Hence, when φ_{all} is fixed, q_o for $\varphi_i = 3.0$ in Fig. 3 (b) is larger than that for $\varphi_i = 1.5$ in Fig. 3 (a). A larger value of q_o therefore extinguishes flames locally.

Regarding the temperature contours measured at $z = 0$ mm in Fig. 3(a), the temperature near the wall surface of the outer tube is low, and then a heat loss effect appears. On the contrary, the temperature measured at $z = 0$ mm in Fig. 3(b) is higher than that in Fig. 3 (a), although the local quenching is observed. These results mean that the heat loss effect for $\varphi_i = 3.0$ is smaller than that for $\varphi_i = 1.5$ when φ_{all} is fixed.

Figures 4 (a) and 4 (b) show the temperature contours of the $r-z$ plane under the same conditions as Figs. 3 (a) and 3 (b). In Fig. 4 (a), the temperature contour is nearly axisymmetric distribution. However, the temperature contour in Fig. 4 (b) is non-axisymmetric distribution so the flame is extinguished locally. Focusing on the downstream from $z = 20$ mm the petal-type flame is formed, and the low-temperature region near the wall in Fig. 4 (a) is expanded toward the downstream due to the heat loss effect. In Fig. 4 (b), although the cooling effect of the wall is observed, the temperature is higher than that in Fig. 4 (a). The above results indicate, although the flames observed in Figs. 3 (b) and 4 (b) are locally extinguished, that unburned gases produced by local quenching are oxygenated in the downstream region from the petal-type flame, and then the exothermal reaction is continued.

(a) $\varphi_i = 1.5, \varphi_{all} = 0.7$

(b) $\phi_i = 3.0, \phi_{all} = 0.7$

Figure 3. Flame appearances and contours of temperature on the $r-\theta$ plane in the combustor

Figure 4. Temperature contours in the combustor on the $r-z$ plane at $\theta = 0^\circ$

Figure 5. Burnt gas temperature at the burner exit ($z = 0$ mm). Figure 6. Heat loss rate. ϕ_i is kept constant, and ϕ_{all} is controlled by changing the air flow rate supplied from the outer tube. ϕ_i is kept constant, and ϕ_{all} is controlled by changing the air flow rate supplied from the outer tube.

3.2 Temperature at the chamber outlet and heat loss rate

Figure 5 shows the variations of the mean temperature at the combustion chamber outlet T_b with the overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} . For comparison, the adiabatic flame temperature obtained by chemical equilibrium computation is also shown in Fig. 5. Although T_b is lower than the adiabatic flame temperature, the difference in temperature becomes small as ϕ_{all} decreases. For overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} larger than 0.8, T_b becomes high with an increase in ϕ_i in the same ϕ_{all} .

Figure 6 shows the variation of the heat loss rate η_{ht} with ϕ_{all} . The η_{ht} becomes small as ϕ_{all} decreases. However, the curves of $\phi_i = 3.0$ and 4.0 are at a minimum at $\phi_{all} = 0.7$ and 0.8 , respectively. Such results relate closely to the extent of local quenching, and are also observed in our previous studies (Suenaga et al., 2010b, 2011b). In the same ϕ_{all} , η_{ht} decreases

with an increase in ϕ_i . This result is obtained due to the following. As stated above, to obtain the same ϕ_{all} , it is necessary to increase the supply air flow rate q_o from the outer tube by increasing ϕ_i . Since the increase in q_o shortens the residence time of reactants in the combustion chamber, η_{hl} at the same ϕ_{all} becomes small with an increase in ϕ_i (Yuasa et al., 2009). Figure 5 shows that the difference between T_b and the adiabatic flame temperature decreases with a decrease in ϕ_{all} , and that T_b at the same ϕ_{all} increases as ϕ_i increases. The reason is also related to the decrease in the residence time of reactants in the combustion chamber. In the present study, the minimum heat loss rate was obtained in the experimental condition $\phi_i = 4.0$ and $\phi_{all} = 0.8$.

3.3 Exergy loss rate

Figure 7 shows the variations of exergy loss rate $\eta_{ex,loss}$ with the overall equivalence ratio ϕ_{all} . $\eta_{ex,loss}$ of the adiabatic flame is also shown in Fig. 7. $\eta_{ex,loss}$ of the adiabatic flame is about 0.35, and $\eta_{ex,loss}$ estimated using the temperature measured in this study is larger than that of the adiabatic flame. This result relates closely to the result of the heat loss rate described above. Namely, as also shown in formula (6), because the exergy loss rate increases with the increase in the heat loss rate and separates from that of the adiabatic flame. In this study, the minimum value of $\eta_{ex,loss}$ obtained in this experiment was 0.57 in the experimental condition $\phi_i = 4.0$ and $\phi_{all} = 0.8$.

According to formula (6), the exergy loss rate is obtained as the sum of the heat loss rate and entropy generation rate. Figures 8 and 9 show the variations of the ratio of the heat loss rate and the entropy generation rate to the exergy loss rate, i.e. $\eta_{hl}/\eta_{ex,loss}$ and $(\eta_{ex,loss} - \eta_{hl})/\eta_{ex,loss}$, with ϕ_{all} respectively. Comparing Fig. 8 with Fig. 9, $\eta_{hl}/\eta_{ex,loss}$ is larger than $(\eta_{ex,loss} - \eta_{hl})/\eta_{ex,loss}$. As a result of the adiabatic flame shown in Fig. 7, entropy generation decreases toward to the stoichiometric equivalence ratio. However, reduction of the exergy loss caused by the increase in ϕ_{all} is slight. Hence, decreasing the heat loss is considered effective for reducing the exergy loss in this combustor.

Figure 7. Exergy loss rate. ϕ_i is kept constant, and ϕ_{all} is controlled by changing the air flow rate supplied from the outer tube.

Figure 8. Proportion of the heat loss rate to the exergy loss rate. ϕ_i is kept constant, and ϕ_{all} is controlled by changing the air flow rate supplied from the outer tube.

Figure 9. Loss rate due to entropy generation. ϕ_i is kept constant, and ϕ_{all} is controlled by changing the air flow rate supplied from the outer tube.

3.4 Performance comparison with the other combustors

Table 1 shows the specifications of various combustor types. The heat loss rate η_{hl} and exergy loss rate $\eta_{ex,loss}$ of the other combustors were obtained by the same method as in our research. The flame in this research is formed in the cylindrical stagnating flow field. The flame used by Marbach et al. (2007) is formed on a porous media surface, the flame by Sakurai et al. (2013) is stabilized in the stagnation flow field, and the flame by Wan et al. (2015) is formed by utilizing the low-speed region of the cavity.

First, our results are compared with the combustor developed by Wan et al. Both combustor volume V_o and chamber volume V_i in the present study are smaller than those of Wan et al. (2015). And further, both η_{hl} and $\eta_{ex,loss}$ are also smaller than those of Wan et al. (2015). Here, the heat outputs L of these combustors are almost the same. Therefore, the stagnating flow type combustor developed in this study outperforms Wan et al.'s combustor.

Next, comparing our combustor with that developed by Sakurai et al. (2013), although our V_i is larger than that of Sakurai et al., V_o is smaller than theirs. Both our η_{hl} and $\eta_{ex,loss}$ are smaller than theirs. Here, the difference between our $\eta_{ex,loss}$ and Sakurai et al. is large, whereas the difference in η_{hl} is small. This is because the equivalence ratio set by them is leaner than ours, and their entropy generation rate becomes higher than ours. As a result, the exergy loss rate is increased. However, the combustor developed by Sakurai et al. is superior in terms of lean combustion.

Finally, we compare our combustor with the combustor developed by Marbach et al. (2007). Both V_o and V_i of Marbach et al. are smaller than ours. Furthermore, both η_{hl} and $\eta_{ex,loss}$ of their combustor are also smaller than ours.

Table 1 Performance comparison with the other meso-scale combustors

	Present study	Methane and air	Propane and air	Methane and air
Fuel and oxidizer	Propane and air	Methane and air	Propane and air	Methane and air
Flame type	Premixed and diffusion flames	Premixed flame	Premixed flame	Premixed flame
Combustion field	Cylindrical stagnation flow	Cavity flow	Stagnation flow	On porous plate
Combustor size V_o [cm ³]	14.1	18.2	22.5	1.5
Chamber size V_i [cm ³]	2.44	5.90	1.26	0.36
Surface to volume ratio [cm ⁻¹]	5.37	5.66	6.98	8.14
Heat loss rate, η_{hl}	0.30 at $\phi_{all} = 0.80$	0.44 at $\phi = 0.90$	0.34 at $\phi = 0.55$	0.14 at $\phi = 0.70$

Exergy loss rate, $\eta_{ex,loss}$	0.57 at $\varphi_{all} = 0.80$	0.68 at $\varphi = 0.90$	0.70 at $\varphi = 0.55$	0.50 at $\varphi = 0.70$
Heat output, L [W]	172 at $\varphi_{all} = 0.80$	179 at $\varphi = 0.90$	160 at $\varphi = 0.55$	90 at $\varphi = 0.70$

Especially, η_{hl} is half of ours, and the difference is 0.16. However, the difference in $\eta_{ex,loss}$ is small, and is 0.07. This is because our setting equivalence ratio is larger than theirs, and our entropy generation rate is lower than theirs. Therefore, reducing the heat loss rate is required to further improve our combustor performance.

In this study, the performance evaluation of the combustor was carried out using the heat loss rate and exergy loss rate. As a result, we were able to evaluate the combustor performance considering the different equivalence ratio conditions. The evaluation by the exergy loss rate is valid for comparison with the performance of the other combustors.

In order to maintain a constant boundary condition of the outer wall, our combustor has installed a water jacket, regardless of the setting equivalence ratio. In the future, by removing the water jacket from the combustor and by making the new combustor using heat-resistant materials, we will develop a high-performance combustor in which advantage of the cylindrical diffusion flame, which is strengthened with the decrease of the flame diameter, is fully exploited.

4. Conclusion

Using the annular type meso-scale combustor with the stagnation flow field of a cylindrical coordinate system, we carried out an experimental study. The combustor consisted of inner and outer tubes, and rich mixture and air were supplied from the inner and outer tubes, respectively. Cylindrical diffusion and rich premixed flames were formed in the combustion chamber. The fuel used was C_3H_8 and the oxidizer used air. To investigate the flame structure, we measured temperature in the combustion chamber by using thermocouples. The temperature measured was used to evaluate the heat loss rate. To evaluate the performance of this combustor, we calculated the exergy loss rate by considering the heat loss rate and entropy generation rate. As results, the minimum values of the heat loss rate and exergy loss rate were 0.30 and 0.57, respectively. Performance comparison with the other meso-scale combustors was made by using the heat loss rate and exergy loss rate. Since the entropy generation rate depends on the setting equivalence ratio, the evaluation by the exergy loss rate is valid for comparison with the performance of the other combustors. In the future, we will work to further improve the performance of the combustor by removing the water jacket and by developing the combustor using heat-resistant materials.

References

- Fan, Y., Suzuki, Y., Kasagi, N., Experimental study of micro-scale premixed flame in quartz channels, Proceedings of the Combustion Institute, Vol. 32, Issue 2 (2009), pp.3083-3090.
- Ju, Y., Cadou, C., and Maruta, K., "Microscale combustion and power generation", Momentum Press (2015)
- Kaskan, Y. E., "The dependence of flame temperature on mass burning velocity", Symposium (International) on Combustion, 6 (1957), pp.134-143.
- Li, Y-H., Li, H.Y, Dunn-Rankin, D., Chao, Y-C., Enhancing thermal, electrical efficiencies of a miniature combustion-driven thermophotovoltaic system, Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications (Prog. Photovolt: Res. Appl.), Vol.17 (2009) pp.502-512.
- Marbach, T. L., Sadasivuni, V., Agrawal, A. K., Investigation of a miniature combustor using porous media surface stabilized flame, Combustion Science and Technology, Vol.179 (2007), pp.1901-1922.
- Mizutani, Y., "Nensho Kogaku 2nd edition", Morikita Publishing Co., Ltd., (1989) (in Japanese).
- Sakurai, T., Yuasa, S., Ono, Y. and Honda, T., "Flame stability and emission characteristics of propane-fueled flat-flame miniature combustor for ultra-micro gas turbine", Combustion and Flame, Vol.160 (2013), pp.2497-2506.
- Shimokuri, D., Hara, T., Matsumoto, R., Development of a small-scale power system with meso-scale vortex combustor and thermo-electric device, Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering, Vol.25, No.10 (2015), 104004.

- Suenaga, Y., Kitano, M., Yanaoka, H., "Extinction of Cylindrical Diffusion Flame", Transactions of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers, Series B, Vol.76, No.770 (2010a), pp.1558-1563 (in Japanese).
- Suenaga, Y., Kitano, M., Yanaoka, H., "Development of Ultra-micro Combustor Using Cylindrical Flames", Transactions of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers, Series B, Vol.76, No.772 (2010b), pp.2258-2263 (in Japanese).
- Suenaga, Y., Kitano, M., Yanaoka, H., "Extinction of Cylindrical Diffusion Flame", Journal of Thermal Science and Technology, Vol.6, No.3, (2011a), pp.323-332.
- Suenaga, Y., Kitano, M., Yanaoka, H., "Development of Ultra-micro Combustor Using Cylindrical Flames", Journal of Thermal Science and Technology, Vol.6, No.3, (2011b), pp.406-415.
- Takagi, T., Okamoto, T., Nishida, K., "Netsu Rikigaku", Osaka University Press, (2006) (in Japanese)
- Wan, J., Fan, A., Liu, Y., Yao, H., Liu, W., Gou, X., Zhao, D., Experimental investigation and numerical analysis on flame stabilization of CH₄/air mixture in a mesoscale channel with wall cavities, Combust. Flame, 162 (2015) pp.1035-1045.
- Yuasa, S., Shimotori, S., Honda, T., Sakurai, T., Sogo, S., "Consideration on burning at high space heating rates in ultra-micro combustors for UMGH", Journal of the Combustion Society of Japan, Vol.51, No.156, (2009), pp.142-148 (in Japanese).